

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Seedling root dip treatments to control gall midge (GM)

D. Sundararaju, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Complex for Goa, Ela, Old Goa, India

We sought to develop a simple, economic method for GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) control. In 1982 kharif we evaluated 8 chlorpyrifos 0.02% treatments for GM control (see table). Unprotected Jaya seedlings (5.3% silvershoots were recorded in the nursery) were planted in a

replicated trial in 5- × 5-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. For the seedling root treatment, rock phosphate at 60 kg P/ha was mixed with wet clay at 3:1 and water was added to make a thick slurry. Chlorpyrifos 20 EC was mixed with the slurry at 0.02% concentration. Seedling roots were uniformly coated with the chlorpyrifos-treated slurry and planted. At planting, the field was puddled with very little standing water.

Because seedlings were GM infested at planting, all treatments had GM incidence even at 15 d after transplanting (DT).

However, incidence increased significantly only in the untreated control up to 45 DT. Beyond 60 DT there was no significant difference in GM infestation between treatments, largely because GM-infested seedlings were planted. Preinfestation treatment is essential. As an alternative to chlorpyrifos seedling root dip for 12 or 3 h, chlorpyrifos-treated carbon phosphate treatments gave good results (see table). Carbon phosphate is commonly used in rice and coconut soils at Goa in kharif. □

Effect of seedling root dip treatments on GM damage and rice grain yield, Goa, India, 1982.^a

Treatment	Silvershoots (%)				Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Gross profit ^b (\$/ha)	Cost of insecticide application ^c (\$/ha)	Net gain ^d (\$/ha)	Gain from insecticide ^e (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ^f
	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT							
SRD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h	3.8 a	2.5 ab	11.4 ab	19.3a	6.4 a	3.4 a	438	6	432	210	36.0
SRD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution for 3 h	6.9 a	1.9 a	8.9 a	25.5 a	5.9 a	2.4 b	319	7	312	90	13.9
SRT with chlorpyrifos 0.02% treated CPS for											
1 min	5.7 a	8.0 c	19.7 c	26.1 a	6.1 a	2.2 b	285	6	279	57	10.5
5 min	3.3 a	7.1 c	18.4 bc	30.1 a	5.5 a	2.1 b	272	6	266	44	8.3
10 min	7.1 a	5.1 bc	15.8 ab	34.0 a	5.5 a	2.3 b	296	6	290	68	12.3
20 min	5.3 a	7.5 c	16.8 bc	26.2 a	5.4 a	2.4 b	319	6	313	91	16.2
30 min	3.5 a	5.5 bc	16.6 bc	26.8 a	5.0 a	2.3 b	300	6	294	72	13.0
Untreated control	5.6 a	20.2 d	32.6 d	27.9 a	4.8 a	1.7 b	222	0	222	—	—

^a Mean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. SRD = seedling root dip, SRT = seedling root treatment, CPS = carbon phosphate slurry, DT = days after transplanting. ^b Yield in kg/ha at 14% moisture × \$0.13. ^c \$1.31 for labor + cost of insecticide including the cost of urea. ^d Gross profit – cost of insecticide application. ^e Net gain of treatment – net gain of control. ^f (Gross profit of treatment – gross profit of control) ÷ cost of insecticide application.

Tyrophagus palmarum (Oudemans) mite in rice seedlings and leaf sheaths

J. Rao and A. Prakash, Division of Entomology, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack 753006, India

The mite *T. palmarum* (Oudemans) (Acaridae: Astigmata) was recorded to infest rice in China. In India, the first recorded mite infestation was observed in rice seedlings and leaf sheaths of Ratna in a 1977 rabi nursery at CRRI. Mite infestations were surveyed in rice nurseries and fields in 1979 and 1982-84.

The mite infested seedlings and leaf sheaths of Ratna, Karuna, CR1009, CR1014, Jaya, Vijaya, Pusa 2-21, Kalinga-I, Supriya, and Jagannath (see table). It was identified at the United States Department of Agriculture Systematic Entomology Department.

Adults and nymphs feed on growing leaves of seedlings, causing a bleached appearance followed by wilting, shriveling, and drying. These symptoms were confirmed by inoculating adult mites on 10-d-old Ratna seedlings and observing mite development under controlled conditions. Inoculating 10

or 100 mites/100 seedlings produced similar symptoms after 15 d. Mite populations varied from 2 to 34 mites/seedling (see table) on 25-d-old seedlings from 1983 dry and wet season nurseries. Mites were counted using a stereoscopic binocular microscope.

T. palmarum has more hairs than most rice-infesting mites. The post-abdominal region has five pair of hairs as long as or longer than the mite's legs. Two pair of hair grow on each side of the anterior abdominal region between the 2d and 3d pair of legs (see figure). The mite is transparent but takes on the

color of feeding materials. It is fast moving and can be seen as a small moving dot on seedlings.

We attempted mass rearing of *T. palmarum* on different diets of fungi grown on several artificial media. It multiplied vigorously on *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Alternaria padwickii*, and *Curvularia* sp. On 10 different media, the mites grew best on 4% oatmeal agar (OMA). Egg-to-egg life cycle took 10-12 d on *F. moniliforme* grown on 4% OMA. Mites produced about 247 eggs, of which 210 hatched. About 167 adults emerged from the hatched larvae. Females reproduced parthenogenetically. There was no male population in the culture. □

***T. palmarum* populations in seedlings and leaf sheaths in 1983 dry and wet season nurseries, Cuttack, India.**

Variety	Populations (adults, juveniles, and eggs) 10 seedlings ^a
Ratna	34 b
Karuna	30 ab
CR1009	28 ab
CR1014	18 ab
Jaya	25 ab
Vijaya	19 ab
Pusa 2-21	2 a
Kalinga-I	16 ab
Supriya	15 ab
Jagannath	19 ab

^aAv of 10 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

T. palmarum mite, Cuttack, India.

Parasitization of yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* eggs

H. S. Kim and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

We surveyed the IRRI farm to determine the extent of parasitization of YSB egg masses. Egg masses were randomly collected at weekly intervals from Jul to Aug 1984 from rice fields, 15-20 d after transplanting, and brought to the laboratory for collection of emerging parasites.

Three species of hymenopterous parasitoids — *Tetrastichus schoenobii*, *Teleonomus rowani*, and *Trichogramma japonicum* — were reared from 455 egg masses (Table 1). *T. schoenobii* was the most abundant among the species, parasitizing 95% of the eggs. *T. schoenobii* may be

the most efficient because two to four (av of three) host eggs are needed to complete the larval period. *T. japonicum* was so small that one to four (av of two) parasites developed from one host egg. Thus, in calculating percent parasitism by *T. schoenobii*, the number of emerged parasites is multiplied by 3. For *T. japonicum*, the number of emerged parasites is divided by 2 (see footnote to Table 1). Female parasites were five times as abundant as males.

Multiparasitization occurs in YSB egg masses (Table 2). Eighty-eight percent of the egg masses were parasitized by one or a combination of parasite species. The highest parasitization (35%) was by a combination of *T. rowani* and *T. japonicum*. □

Table 2. Multiparasitization of YSB egg masses (n = 485) by 3 parasites, IRRI, Jul-Aug 1984.

Parasite combination	Parasitization of egg masses (%)
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. schoenobii</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	9.8
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	34.6
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. schoenobii</i>	17.7
<i>T. schoenobii</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	11.5
<i>T. schoenobii</i>	9.5
<i>T. rowani</i>	3.2
<i>T. japonicum</i>	1.2
Total	87.5

Table 1. Percent parasitization of YSB egg masses and the sex ratio of the parasitoids, IRRI, Jul-Aug 1984.

Parasite	Egg masses (no.)	Eggs parasitized ^a (%)	Parasites (no./egg mass)		Stem borer larvae (no./egg mass)		Sex ratio (male:female)
			Emerged	Unemerged	Hatched	Unhatched	
<i>T. schoenobii</i>	46	94.7	18.7	2.0	1.5	2.0	5:1:1
<i>T. rowani</i>	15	45.3	20.8	10.3	18.4	19.1	5:3:1
<i>T. japonicum</i>	6	8.1	10.0	3.0	63.8	9.9	4:7:1

^aCalculated as: $T. schoenobii = \frac{(C \times 3) + (D \times 3)}{(A + D) + (C \times 3) + (D \times 3)} \times 100$

$T. rowani = \frac{C+D}{A+B+C+D} \times 100$

$T. japonicum = \frac{C/2 + D}{A + B + (C/2) + D} \times 100$

Where A = no. of hatched stem borer larvae, B = no. of unhatched stem borer larvae, C = no. of emerged parasites, and D = no. of unemerged parasites.

A simple technique of rearing yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker)

F. G. Medrano and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

Insecticide evaluation and host plant resistance studies using YSB have been limited by an inadequate insect supply during certain months. Previous workers made unsatisfactory mass rearing attempts by placing larvae on 40- to 45-d-old rice plants or cut stem pieces of flowering plants, or feeding them artificial diets.

We developed a simple mass rearing technique using healthy booting stage rice plants. IR62 is used as a food plant because it is early maturing, high tillering, and YSB susceptible, but is resistant to several other insects and diseases that may infest a greenhouse culture.